

ISic3358

Inscribed funerary altar

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary altar

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Necropolis of Grotticelli, excavated January 1929, from among several Christian/ Byzantine tombs. Found along with various lamps, bowls, amphorae/ alabastron and other elements, although these had been moved in antiquity from the tomb itself (so the museum inventory)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 48604

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 83 cm

Width 41 cm

Depth 38 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ΑΥΟΤ[]
2. χρηστὲ καὶ
3. ἄμεμπτε
4. χαῖρε ζήσης
5. ἔτη αβ'
6. μῆνες α'

Apparatus

Text based upon autopsy

2-3 letters follow but are impossible to decipher

The traces at the end of the line are compatible with καὶ

Translation (en)

Worth and blamless [---], farewell! You lived [-?] years and 11(?) months

Commentary

The stone appears to be unpublished. The name of the deceased is indecipherable. The age in years appears clearly on the stone as αβ, but this is not a standard numeral and it is not obvious how to translate it; the age in months appears to be written in reverse (a phenomenon well attested in Hellenistic Sicily), in which case it is 11.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644863

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3358. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358436>

140. Stone Column - East Cultural Region, Chittagong, 1980s. No. 140/1980/14

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
06/05/2014